

Ultrashort electric pulses: a way to sensitize cancer stem cells

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Medulloblastoma (MB) is the most common pediatric malignant brain tumor, its conventional therapy consists of surgical resection followed by chemotherapy and radiotherapy that often involve severe neurocognitive deficiencies. Cancer stem cells (CSCs) seem to be candidates in the onset of the disease and constitute an endless reserve for the maintenance and progression of the tumor. These cells could be the reason of conventional therapy failure, maintaining a quiescence state that is the survival strategy responsible for later recurrence and relapse of the disease. Therefore, new therapeutic strategies are necessary to specifically target CSCs that escape from conventional treatments [1]. The aim of this study is to attempt to selectively target quiescent CSCs using suitable pulse electric fields (PEFs). Recently, pulsed electric fields in the microsecond and nanosecond time scale have been delivered to different cell types reporting different and interesting effects without thermal heating [2-4]. Our hypothesis is that the electric treatment would make CSCs more sensitive to radiotherapy by inducing stress effects, and or differentiation.

Therefore, as first step, different MB cell lines (D283, D341 and DAOY) were characterized in terms of their CSCs content. The D283 cells resulted a perfect model of MB SCs. They showed almost 100% of CD133 positive cells defining their high oncogenic potential, a major capacity to form neurospheres and to engraft in nude mice with respect to the other characterized cell lines.

Cell exposure was performed in standard electroporation cuvette using a suitable pulsing buffer [5, 6]. Different sets of delivered pulses were taken into account: microsecond pulses last 40 μ s with an amplitude of 0.35 MV/m, while nanosecond pulses last 300 ns with an amplitude of 1.1 MV/m. A variable number of pulses were also taken into account.

We analyzed different biological end points at different times after the exposure as: i) cell viability, ii) cell permeabilization, iii) cell cycle, iv) reactive oxygen species formation, as well as a panel of different genes involved in cell cycle, apoptosis and differentiation.

However, a crucial point for the effectiveness of this novel treatment strategy involves the selective

neutralization of CSCs. To this aim normal human astrocyte (NHA), as a model of non-transformed cells, were exposed to similar electric stimulations. NHA presented different responses with respect to D283 in term of cell membrane permeabilization, cell viability and cell cycle perturbation.

The evidenced selectivity of the electric treatment is very interesting for its potentiality in real therapeutic applications. Indeed, a combined treatment PEFs-ionizing radiation could represent an innovative strategy to improve clinical outcomes of MB in a near future.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 737164 Sumcastec.

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